

Soil and crop management

A quick method of evaluating straw decomposition in flooded soil

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Rice straw has an important role in maintaining soil fertility. When incorporated into the soil, rice straw stimulates microbial activity. Its role in increasing soil fertility is dependent on the rate of its decomposition in the field. This work was undertaken to study the rate of rice straw decomposition in the field.

Air-dried rice straw was cut into 2- to 3-cm pieces. One gram was put into 5- × 7-cm bag made of nylon net with a 0.7-mm opening. The bags were placed in 10-cm depth of soil in the rice field at IRRI in September, and then were taken out at 20, 40, 60, and 80 days after incubation. The straw from each bag was gently rinsed once in distilled

Changes in rice straw during its decomposition in the soil. ^a

	0	Day 20	Day 40	Day 60	Day 80
Wt of straw per bag (g)	1.00	0.69 ± 0.04	0.54 ± 0.036	0.50 ± 0.05	0.39 ± 0.05
Ash per bag (g)	0.18	0.22 ± 0.03	0.21 ± 0.037	0.22 ± 0.036	0.19 ± 0.05
Organic matter per bag (g)	0.82	0.46 ± 0.018	0.33 ± 0.019	0.28 ± 0.027	0.21 ± 0.012
Decrease in organic matter/bag (g)		0.36	0.49	0.55	0.61
Total N (%)	0.47	0.60 ± 0.04	0.83 ± 0.058	1.03 ± 0.07	1.12 ± 0.13
Increase in N %		0.13	0.36	0.56	0.65

^a Mean and standard deviation (5 replications).

water and the dry weight, ash, and total N% were measured to study the decomposition pattern (see table). Organic matter was determined by ignition loss.

Dry weight and the organic matter of straw per bag decreased rapidly up to 40 days, and then decomposition slowed

down. There was a 46% reduction in dry weight and 60% in organic matter of straw per bag during the 40-day period. The ash content of straw/bag remained more or less the same throughout the period. The total N% of straw increased rapidly up to 60 days (see table). ■

A simple method for middle-term preservation of azolla germplasm

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Thirty-two strains of azolla including all species except *A. nilotica* and *A. microphylla* have been collected at IRRI. Proper maintenance of this germplasm is a problem. A method was developed to preserve the germplasm for 100 days or more without reinoculation.

The healthy fronds of azolla, grown in the greenhouse or in the field, are washed with tap water. About 100 shoot tips (each with several young leaves) are cut from the fronds and enclosed in small nylon bags. The shoot tips are treated with 2% sodium hypochlorite and 0.1% Polysorbate solution to eliminate algae and other pests epiphytic on the shoot tips. After 2-3 minutes in the solution, the shoot tips are washed sev-

eral times with sterilized distilled water. About 10 shoot tips are placed in 50-ml Erlenmeyer flasks with cotton plugs, each containing 20 ml sterilized nitrogen-free nutrient medium (Holst medium). The inoculations are cultivated in 25°/21°C (12 hours day, 12 hours night) under 12 klux light intensity and 75% relative humidity. Normal fronds are formed from the shoot tips in 2-3 weeks. These clones, which are free from epiphytic algae and other pests, are transferred to 15° / 15°C (12 hours day/ 12 hours night) under about 1 klux fluorescent light for preservation.

Healthy fronds are repropagated from the preserved clones. Preserved material transferred to suitable growth conditions after 100 days are a normal green and retain nitrogen-fixing activity.

An *Anabaena-azollae-free* clone of *A. pinnata* (Tancheng strain) obtained from the Botany Institute of the Chinese Academy of Sciences was also preserved and has remained viable. ■

Effect of presowing moisture regimes and farmyard manure on the forms of iron and manganese in soils and on yield of rice

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A greenhouse experiment on calcareous (pH 8.4, organic carbon 0.5%, and CaCO₃ 7.2%) and noncalcareous (pH 8.2, organic carbon 0.62%, and CaCO₃ 1.0%) Vertisols (Vertic Ustropepts) during the 1980 summer studied the effect of adding farmyard manure (0 and 0.75%) and of moisture regimes (dry, saturated, and 3-cm submergence) 15 days before sowing, on the forms of iron (Fe) and manganese (Mn) in soils and on the yield of rice cultivar Tul-japur 1.

Exchangeable Fe and Mn in both soils increased with an increase in pre-